

THE FIELD OF MANAGEMENT AND ITS DEVELOPMENT IN
UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *this article analyzes the importance of the field of management today, its role in the development of enterprises and the economy, and the works that are being carried out for its development in Uzbekistan. Modern management that is being formed in Uzbekistan is a comprehensive science of innovation, which is the formation of a market economy, the development of entrepreneurship, the creation of certain conditions and competitiveness, the creation of a favorable ground for revitalizing the activity of physical and legal forms based on economic freedom and responsibility. is born at the same time.*

Keywords. *Management, enterprises, economy, innovation, investment, market economy, entrepreneurship, competitiveness.*

The founders of management theory are Taylor, Ford, Gilbert, Emerson, Fayol and others. Historically, the initial direction of management theory was named "classical" (traditional) school. American engineer and researcher Frederic Taylor contributed greatly to the creation of this school. Taylor has held all levels of service - from junior clerk to manager of a large metallurgical enterprise in Boston, USA.

He applied a scientific approach to the organization of some production processes and management of the entire enterprise in the first decision. His famous

works such as "Fundamentals of scientific enterprise management", "Principles and methods of scientific organization of management", "Administrative-technical organization of industrial enterprises" are the basis of a large collection of literature on scientific organization of production management published abroad.

Taylor justified the need for special functional management of labor processes, tried to separate the organization of production into structural elements along with physical labor. In the scheme developed by him, it is reflected that it is impossible to work casually, everything is thought out in advance, all conditions and methods of work must be clearly defined in advance. Management as a field of science is an interdisciplinary network, in which achievements made in economics, sociology, psychology, law, technical and other sciences, as well as experiences in the art of management are expressed.

The subject of management is to study the laws (laws), principles and relations of management at all levels of economic management. Management relations are an integral part of socio-economic relations and have various economic, organizational, social, labor, psychological and other forms.

Management relations represent a complex set of communication and interaction between employees under management, therefore, management is primarily the management of people. It is not difficult to imagine the activities of thousands of enterprises based on different ownership in the market economy. Organization of the management of enterprises at one or another level depends on the management ability of the head of the enterprise. His ability is measured by the extent to which he has acquired knowledge in the field of management. From this point of view, the word "management" has become one of the words associated with the market economy in our lives.

Management is an English word ("management"), and in Uzbek it means management, organization, leadership. It is a form of enterprise management in the market economy. Management means organization and management of economic

and social spheres of human life on the basis of business. Although the English word "management" means management, originally it meant to bring down horses. Later, this term began to be used for a two-wheeled cart. Today, it is about managing people and teams. In this place, it is understood to achieve the goals by using people's work and will. But management should not be understood only as a process of managing people.

The meaning of the word "Management" in English is extremely complex. In the basic Oxford dictionary of the English language, you can find the following interpretations of this word:

- 1) way of dealing with people;
- 2) the art of power and management;
- 3) a specific type of business;
- 4) administrative task.

Thus, the term "Management" means the following:

- management;
- the field of knowledge in the human body;
- the social layer of those who implemented management.

Management is an independent form of professional activity, which is the achievement of the intended goal by effective use of material and labor resources as a result of voluntary economic activity of the firm in market conditions. This goal is achieved based on the principles and methods of the economic mechanism of management.

Management means management of the market economy under market conditions, that is:

➤ to direct the company to the demands and needs of the market, to the needs of specific customers, and on this basis to organize the production of products that will bring the intended profit to the company;

- always striving to increase production efficiency with minimum costs while achieving optimal results;
- independence of economic activity;
- continuous improvement of goals and plans, taking into account the market situation;
- in the market, in the process of exchange, the final result of the firm or its independent economic activity departments and parts is shown;
- extensive use of modern databases and computers for the implementation of multivariate accounting - books in making informed and optimal decisions.

The word control is used in a broad sense, for example: control of a state, control of a machine, control of a biological process, etc. The word "management" is mainly used in the management of socio-economic processes in market conditions at the company level. Management unites workers with various independence, that is, engineers, designers, economists, statisticians, psychologists, accountants. All these are managed by the manager. A manager is free from ownership of the capital of the firm he works for, so he may or may not own shares of the firm.

When giving the definition of management, the economic activity of the firm is manifested in the following:

- ✓ in the voluntary sector of the economy, i.e. in industrial enterprises, banking, transport, etc.
- ✓ voluntary activity of the company, i.e. in production, scientific research, finance, supply, etc.

The purpose of the company's economic activity is to provide the production process with all the necessary resources and organize the technical period (cycle), which means applying the results of scientific research to production, creating and improving production technology, and raising the quality level of the product. , implementation of commercial activities, execution of goods

movement operations, implementation of various accounts, material and technical support of the production process, provision of financial resources, etc. One of the main issues of management is setting the company's goals for the near or far future, that is, for the future. For this, it is necessary to assess the company's capabilities and know whether it is provided with resources.

As a result of the rational use of material and labor resources, people or groups cooperating in the process of management with minimum cost and maximum efficiency can achieve the goal. Management has its own economic mechanism to solve socio-economic, technical, socio-psychological issues that arise in the course of economic activity.

This economic mechanism of management consists of 3 parts:

- ❖ management within the company;
- ❖ production management;
- ❖ personnel management.

Economic management is the management of organizations, institutions, enterprises and firms within a certain framework, in which management of the labor team, personnel (employees) and workers is of particular importance. Such an important part of economic management is related to the field of management. Since management is a field related to the effective combination of all types of resources (ie, natural, labor, financial, etc.) requires a decision.

In economic management, the object of direct management consists of labor teams and individual employees. Only the material elements of production, i.e. labor tools and objects, are affected by means of their labor activity. The most basic cognitive method of management is the dialectical method, which helps management to reveal the essence of the studied social phenomena. The following other methods are also characteristic of management: a clear historical approach to the study of real events; structural approach, structural analysis, economic

experience, etc., which allow simultaneous analysis of all elements of the economic mechanism and the development of complete management decisions.

The skill of management consists in having the ability to master all his methods, to use them in the right way, to find the most effective one in each specific situation. The continuous operation of all management is management. This is the work process of the control apparatus. In general, management can be described as follows: from the point of view of technology (how it is done), organization (by whom and in what order) and content (what exactly is done).

Management from an economic point of view is, first of all, a system of managing all economic problems, managing people. From the social point of view, management is, first of all, meeting the social requirements of labor teams, educating a person. The management process technology is the practical work performed by the employees of the management apparatus. Thus, the management process is the coordinated operation of the head of the management apparatus and people in order to achieve the set problem.

At the problem stage, the main contradictions in the current state of the system and what needs to be done to improve the system's work are determined. The decision stage is the activity of the leader to move to practical work. As soon as the decision is made, the controlled systems are clearly affected, and some simple control actions are performed.

A functional analysis of the management process establishes the scope of work for each function, determines the number of managers and designs the management system.

a) coordination - the arrival of all management functions in solving technical, economic, social issues together. From this, mutual communication is established, a warning is issued if there is a deviation from the current norms and regulatory documents.

b) stimulation is the activation of the human factor on the basis of broad democracy, management of care in his interests;

c) accounting and control - this is control and accounting of the state of the managed system, management of ensuring work in a uniform manner.

If the controlled object has its own properties, the control functions will also work. However, in the form of an enterprise, the following functions can be distinguished:

- a) main production management;
- b) auxiliary production management;
- c) product quality management;
- d) labor and salary management, etc.

Each specific function is a component of the management function, which in turn is further divided into several parts. Examples include basic production management, marketing, planning, promotion, etc.

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